

IMPROVING IELTS READING SKILL THROUGH DIFFERENT READING STRATEGIES

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Abstract: This article talks about the study of the study of reading strategy as one of the important elements in the development of students' reading technique. But many teachers lack a solid foundation for teaching these reading comprehension strategies. Thus, teachers need to be prepared on how to develop effective comprehension strategies and how to teach these strategies to their IELTS learners.

Therefore, this article will help you learn effective reading strategies to improve your reading skills in IELTS classes. This study is conducted among 15 students in an integrated intermediate skills course. Key research question: Will reading strategies help my students improve their IELTS reading comprehension? The result of the study shows that students improved their skills to a great extent by learning reading strategies.

KEY WORDS: Reading strategies, scanning, skimming, focusing on key words, following the instructions carefully, action research.

INTRODUCTION

The IELTS reading test is designed to assess a wide range of reading skills, including how well learners read for general sense of a passage, read for main ideas, read for details, understand inferences and implied meaning.

According to Hazan Hayaloglu many candidates find the length of the texts to be the most challenging aspect of the IELTS reading section. With three long texts totalling around 2.750 words and just one hour to read them and answer 40 questions, it's clear there is not enough time to go through the texts thoroughly. So, learning some simple reading techniques will really help (2021).

Research shows good readers are actively involved with the text, and they are aware of the processes they use to understand what they read.

Teachers can help improve students' comprehension through instruction of reading strategies; scanning, skimming, focusing on key words, and following the instructions carefully. It is important to teach the strategies by naming the strategy and how it should be used, modelling through the thinking, aloud process, group practice, partner practice and independent use of the strategy (Duke and Pearson 2005).

1.1 Scanning

Scanning means reading a text quickly in order to find specific information. For the IELTS reading test this will be the information to students to answer a question. Scanning is another everyday skill which students use it, for example when deciding what to watch on TV, learners should scan the programme titles and the times they're on and then they skim through the descriptive blurb to help them decide what they want to watch.

Skimming

Another strategy that the good readers employ when comprehending a text is skimming. Skimming means to read the text quickly in order to understand the general meaning. When skimming readers do not read each word to study the text in detail. Learners are just getting the gist of what it's about. Skimming is one of the key IELTS reading skills because once

students understand what the text is about, it will be easier to find the specific information, they need to answer the questions. Understanding the general meaning of a text will help students to scan for the correct information and find the right answer.

1.2 Focusing on key words.

Texts in the IELTS reading section are packed with lots of new vocabulary students mustn't be discoured, learners don't need to understand every word and they can always use contextual clues to guess the meaning of a word that they don't understand. What really matters are keywords. Students should read the question carefully, and underline the keywords. Try to predict what words or phrases will help them to locate the right part of the text and think about other ways of saying these words. What are the synonyms and antonyms. Try to paraphrase. For example if the question says **joint** remember that this means **together** or **shared**.

1.3 Following the instructions carefully.

If the instructions state to use **one word only** students would make sure they don't write more than one word. For questions where they need to fill in missing words make sure the resulting sentence is grammatically accurate students should be particularly careful about singular and plural forms. Also pay attention to spelling and capitalization.(Holschun. Jand Nist. S 2000).

2. Action research question

The area of focus of this research is to improve IELTS reading comprehension by the help of using reading tips. The teacher researcher hopes that without a solid foundation of reading strategies the students will struggle throughout their academic and adults life.

The researcher beliefs to provide reading awareness to her students by teaching reading comprehension strategies and by this way the students will develop a more meaningful reading experience.

The research question is "Would reading strategies help my students to improve their IELTS reading comprehension?,, The aim of this study is to analyze the improvement the students reading skills after they have taken presentations on reading strategies.

METHOD

Reading proficiency is the most fundamental skill for academic learning and success in school. The objective of this research project was to find out the reading awareness level of the students and improve their reading strategies. The teacher researcher used four strategies; scanning, skimming, focusing on key words and following the instructions carefully. The strategies were introduced to the students and practiced for 10 weeks.

RESULT AND CONCLUSION

The result of the reading awareness scale and my personal experience showed that there was a lack of knowledge in the area of reading strategies in my students at the beginning of the study. The student had a lack of knowledge and practice in reading strategies but after a comprehensive study, there was an improvement in their success. At the beginning as being a researcher, I had some worries about how to implement the strategies in the classroom. The number of the strategies was another obstacle as the learners might have found them confusing. Another question in mind was about the success of the students using the comprehension strategies independently as many of these reading comprehension strategies were new to the students. In order to overcome this situation, I had to guide and control the

students in every step of the process especially for the scanning, skimming strategies. After an intensive study I have experienced the improvement in my students. This research journey was quite rewarding both for my students and me. The result of the action research gave me the confidence about how to integrate the strategies into my curriculum. As for the students; they developed a better understanding of the tips and their comprehension in reading have developed. The action research was a productive experience; now that I have seen an increased understanding of reading comprehension strategies and an improvement in reading comprehension of my students, I would like to continue using these strategies in my curriculum.

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